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Impact of Skill-Development Programme in Pottery Industry: A Study in Andro Village, Imphal East District, Manipur

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ABSTRACT

The section of individuals who solely belong to the pottery profession is mostly 'Lois' in Andro, Imphal East, Manipur. The socio-economic status of Andro people has been worsening, and as a result, these workers are moving to another due to the diminishing prospects of the pottery industry. Against this setting, an endeavor has been made to inspect the financial states of the designated populaces. The paper explored a few arising alternatives which can provide some livelihood opportunities considering the government and other agencies taking initiatives for rural industrialization. Primary data were used for the study and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. The findings indicate that socio-economic conditions of the target populations are not improving but there are huge scopes for developing the pottery industry in Andro.

INTRODUCTION

Making stoneware is an immortal occupation, and the best potters through the ages have a nature of agelessness that rises above ordered and social limits. Pottery items are a particular piece of the visual culture of native people groups in many pieces of the world. The magnificence and meaning of our study lies in the fact that pottery has been viewed as the main occupation by the Andro (sc) people since decades. The incomes of the potters have declined over the course of the years rather than increasing in line with the economy's development. Hence, it is vital to undertake a far reaching and logical investigation of Potters, Profession and their Livelihood Opportunities under Rural Skill Development in regards to the diminishing economic status of this community. The contribution made by the craft business towards the national economy, especially in the Manipur state is negligible because of its being unorganized status with the extra limitations of absence of training, low capital, lack of knowledge about new innovations, lack of market knowledge, and a poor institutional system.

The craft traditions in India survived for 5,000 years and appeared mature and firmly established in the Indus Valley's cities later on. Artisans in the cities have discovered the use of wheel and control of fire which led to the transformation of his methods of transport and the tools with which he moulded his clay pots.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Anjali Pandey (2019) studied the Indian conventional approach to making potters in anyway different structures and numerous items delivered by craftsmans for the utilization of individuals in urban areas, towns or ancestral social orders. Jaipur is notable for its craftsmanship. Some

are utilized for home style, while others are for pragmatic purposes. Blue pottery is a joined craft of China's Glazing method and Persian improving expertise and pride for Jaipur.

According to Ritumani Haloi (2017), the socio economic status of the designated populaces is not expanding. There are a lot of prospects to work on their social and financial status by promoting rural industries, including pottery. Vocation open doors are recognized, and it is normal that assuming such modern units are laid out, it will increase employment generation among the Hira people group individuals and the jobless young people of different communities. The paper essentially focused on pottery craft of marginalized Hira community area. It, consequently, has been given to emphasise on various aspects of this industry that will enhance the socio economic development.

Skill Development through Non-Formal Education for National Development in India was analysed by Banhi and Vandana (2015), examining the developing agreement among researchers. The findings revealed that the effectiveness of imparting skill training in employment-oriented courses to the target population segment on a nationwide scale relies on a complex participatory approach by the government, non-government agencies, and institutes of higher education to enhance the efforts of non-formal educational organizations.

Ankul and Pandey (2017) analysed India's skills development system, particularly the challenges in training the youth, focusing on the current state of education, skills development, and employment for Indian youth. The study found that children were unaware of modern technology, which stimulates the development and growth of the country. The skill development programme

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is a powerful weapon to develop creative skills and technical training for the country's young population. It motivates the youth to enhance self-development and self-entrepreneurship by providing training of various activities. It also offers financial assistance through loans at a low rate of interest

On Nei (2011) emphasized non-formal learning by examining the concept and its application in music learning. The idea of non-formal learning falls outside the informal and formal learning categories. Compared to formal learning with a clear and highly structured curriculum, an instruction plan, a sequential learning process, a clear assessment plan, and a person in charge, the non-formal learning does not have the assessment and intended learning outcomes.

Livelihoods

Livelihoods are ways of keeping oneself meaningful and occupied by using one's endowments (human and material) that generate adequate resources requirements for household sustainability. Household members use their capabilities and assets to carry out activities to gain livelihoods. Livelihood opportunities can be impacted by factors in the external environment, and these factors determine the vulnerability context in which households operate (Stage et al., 2002).

The National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) is a Public-Private Partnership (PPP) model in India under the Ministry of Skill Development & Entrepreneurship (MSDE), Government of India. It aims to promote skill development by catalyzing large, quality, for-profit vocational institutions.

Concept of Skill Development

A growing number of countries have achieved the goal of universal primary education, and others are moving closer to this goal. Young people who expect to pursue further education and training to improve their chances of employment and higher income from these goals.

Skill Development

According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), "Skill development is vital in stimulating a sustainable development process and can contribute to facilitating the transition from an informal to formal economy. It is also important to address the opportunities and challenges to meet new demands of changing economies and new technologies in the era of globalization." The contribution development is to develop a workforce empowered with the required upgraded skills, knowledge and internationally recognized qualifications to gain access to enable to tap the employment opportunities that will increase India's competitiveness globally. It aims to increase the productivity of workforce and employability both in the organized and the unorganized sectors. It seeks increased participation from all sections of society including youth, women, disabled and other disadvantaged sections. It

synergizes the efforts of various industries, and enhances the present system with the improved capability to adapt to changing technologies and labour market demands. Skill development is inevitable for the economic growth of a country. Simultaneously, the growth in the manufacturing and tertiary sector is also required to boost the economy to grow exceptionally. India is said to have a skilled workforce of 500 million by 2022 (Business Standard, Jan 13, 2015). The government has taken numerous initiatives to empower women through skill development by launching different schemes like Support to Training & Employment Program STEP, Priyadarshini, Swadhar Greh/ Short Stay Scheme, SABLE, Skill Up-gradation and Training Programme for women in border/ Backward/Tribal Districts etc.

Empowerment

Empowerment means a shift from a delicate situation to accomplishing supremacy that enables a greater access to knowledge and resources. Empowerment liberates women, easing their mobility, decision-making capacity, and awareness of rights, duties and opportunities. Women carry accurate perceptions, priorities and strengths resulting from their life experiences, which are frequently diverse from men's.

They normally make different choices. Empowerment includes higher literacy levels, educational attainment, awareness of rights and responsibilities, active participation in economic activities, better healthcare, equal access to productive resources and improvement in the standard of living. It also includes encouraging the mass through economic development and providing new technology to the people.

Objectives of the study.

1. To identify the problems in the pottery production community members.
2. To evaluate the suitable intervention that has been taken to improve the community's pottery production project.
3. To analyse the present status and socio-economic conditions of the artisans/ workers associated with the pottery industry.

METHODOLOGY

The study has adopted the purposive sampling technique. The study was conducted at Andro village, Imphal east, Manipur, India. The sample size is determined at this level after considering several factors such as time, money efforts and volume of work. The researcher has used primary data and collected it through a field survey. The preliminary data was collected by conducting a field survey of 20 sample respondents with the help of a well-structured questionnaire in the Andro village. Secondary data were obtained through various documents, including District profiles, household budget surveys, and copies of the census and other essential data records. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data collected from the survey were analyzed and interpreted as follows:

Around 42% of the respondents are male, below 30 years of age, and more benefited due to national skills India development programmes. The findings indicate that most of the respondents are educated up to the secondary level. There is a problem of unemployment among the village or localities. The government of India takes necessary steps to reduce the unemployment problem by running a skills development programme. Still, government skill development programmes and schemes are far behind in this area. The respondents have undergone the skill development programme in different areas, which helps them develop their quality of skills and motivates them in their overall development. However, they received only the skill-development programme inherited from their father i.e. from generation to generation, which they're ancestrally provided to them. The respondents had faced severe problems setting up their own business even after getting trainings. In the study, we find there are problems in their day-to-day life and as a result there is a need for proper training and a marketing system to become economically stable.

Table 1: Contribution of the pottery industry in rural economy development

Contribution of the pottery industry in rural economy development	Yes	No
No. of respondents	20	0
Percentage (%)	100	0

Source: Survey.

They revealed that 100 per cent of respondents agreed that the pottery sector contributes to economic development for many rural artisans and craftsmen in the study area (table 1). This is a significant contribution of the potter sector to the rural economy in Manipur and the study area in particular. They make weaving and crafts after the engagement of their agricultural activity, and the entire products have been sold to agents (Intermediaries), local business people and directly to the consumers in the market of Manipur in consideration of cash and this way, people of the rural economy has been getting improving to some extends. In Manipur, pottery helps in earning their income. They also do other jobs along with the pottery. This pottery industry has been continuing from generation to generation. So, they keep in touch with these arts and pass this art to future generations.

During the field survey, the researcher focused on knowing the economic benefits of the pottery industry in the study area. A developing economy is a micro and small industry that became a backbone for its financial structure through vast employment opportunities for

Table 2: Income levels of rural artisans and craftsmen.

Increase Income level	Yes	No
Total respondents	15	5
Percentage (%)	75%	25%

Source: Survey.

its people, by creating industrial estate, which makes decentralization of industries and equal distribution of income and power of purchasing. Scholar has attempted to know the views of rural artisan and artisans to tell that pottery industries provide a self-dependent economy in the study area. The result of the survey is presented in table 2. The artisans and craftsman get some benefits through the pottery industry.

Table 3: Need for skill-Development Programme

Need of skill- Development Programme	Yes	No
Total sample (20)	16	4
Percentage (%)	80%	20%

Source: Survey.

The study found some of the major problems such as lack of local experts on pottery producers within community members, donor dependency Projects, Inadequate skills on pottery producers and inadequate funds for business operation. The community at Andro village has inadequate skills in pottery production, lack of appropriate technology due to lack of training, modern technology machine and experiences and learning from others like field visits. Inadequate access to financial resources has been identified as a core problem thereby becoming a source for other issues to persist in the community. Other problems include inability to get modern skill development programmes and schemes provided by central and state governments. The area (Andro) lacks the current skill, technology, and techniques. If the government offers a new skill Development programme and scheme like PMKVY, skill India, etc., these areas will develop to large extent. Skills and human capital have become the backbone of economic prosperity and social

Table 4: Encourage Rural Entrepreneurship

Encourage Rural Entrepreneurship	Yes	No	May be
Total sample (20)	Nil	20	Nil
Percentage (%)	Nil	100	Nil

Sources: Field data/survey.

well-being in the 21st-century.

Some of the major problems related to entrepreneurship include lack of entrepreneurship skills, low income and lack of financial institutions to access loans. It targeted the community members of Andro (pottery producer group) dependants. Problems like unorganized business, poor exposure to new technologies, lack of marketing facilities, intelligence, and an inadequate institutional framework must be tackled effectively. Assuming demographic advantages of the Andro people, heritage skill of pottery making art, growing demand for fashionable earthen pots, new business opportunities under the Look Act Policy, and increasing border trade relationships with the neighbouring state and countries, the pottery industry can be developed within its perspective. Measures like economic non-potters Profession and their Livelihood Opportunity under Rural economic can be implemented towards bettering the multiple problems associated with

the pottery industry. Again, the craftspeople in this scheduled caste community must change their mindset and ponder their work and culture. Government should come forward to revive industry. It will help boost the socio-economic conditions of the rural artisans-a vulnerable section of the society who has been supplying some essential items since time immemorial to meet social, cultural and religious needs. Skills and human capital have become the backbone of economic prosperity and social well-being in the 21st century.

The Government of India provides many funds for promoting the rural economy and industry. The findings suggest that the availability of funds is not the only factor for rural development. The primary factor seems to be the potential of the funding Ministries/ State Governments to formulate appropriate schemes and the delivery system to utilize funds successfully and adequately move the projects into desired outcomes. To achieve growth, rural areas need productive activities that produce rural exports: goods and services traded outside rural areas. The artisans have inherent skills in pottery which is a strength for them to excel in the pottery industry. However, the lack of modern technology, skill development programme and schemes become a hurdle in competing with this modern world and as a result, the pottery becomes a secondary work for them. If the government provides their requirement, they can easily overcome and find a market for export to neighbouring states and even countries because Manipur is the gateway to Southeast Asia.

CONCLUSION

The significant finding of this study is that the people of Andro Village need the increased income because pottery production is the highest business activity in which the majority of them are engaged. During the survey, most of the respondents are continuing their pottery business. But their own business must have increased their income rationally to have a meaningful living standard of the artisans. The income level is affected by various reasons including poor knowledge of small business management, low level of entrepreneurial education, lack of financial resources to foster their business, lack of capacity to understand the income-generating activities to own business and lack of marketing facilities and lack of modern development programme. There is a need for intervention to ensure that they have to compete on this competitive advantage to the business development. Based on the survey findings, it is understandable that the people group at Andro can continue their business activities if their income increases. The study clearly shows that the socio-economic status of the artisans and craftsmen of pottery industry at Andro are not increasing, even though there are plenty of scopes to improve their social and economic status by developing rural industries, including pottery. Finding also shows

that the development gap in the sample villages is due to poor human capital. They need more modern technology for government agencies' skill development programmes and schemes. The pottery craft business is facing many occupational challenges out of which the major one constitutes a setback for the company that include the inability to secure bank capital loans or a government-assisted loan scheme to purchase modern equipment that leads to slow progress.

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